

Supplementary Table 1. Comparison of clinical characteristics between the non-PDR and PDR groups in patients aged < 60 years.

Variables	non-PDR (n = 51)	PDR (n = 17)	P Value
Male, n (%)	33 (64.7)	12 (70.6)	0.772
Age (years)	47 [43-53]	51 [48-54]	0.140
Height (cm)	165 (8)	168 (8)	0.233
Body weight (kg)	75.9 [69.0-89.8]	76.8 [66.7-88.8]	0.893
BMI (kg/m ²)	28.4 [25.0-34.2]	27.7 [24.9-30.8]	0.346
ECW (L)	14.6 (2.6)	15.8 (2.8)	0.124
ICW (L)	23.4 (4.2)	23.9 (3.6)	0.669
ECW/TBW	0.385 [0.379-0.389]	0.392 [0.389-0.402]	< .0001
BFM (kg)	26.7 [19.3-36.6]	22.8 [15.7-30.4]	0.172
WHR	0.95 (0.07)	0.89 (0.10)	0.018
SMM (kg)	28.6 (5.5)	29.2 (4.7)	0.668
LBM (kg)	51.6 (9.2)	53.7 (8.4)	0.423
BMC (kg)	2.8 (0.5)	3.0 (0.4)	0.242
SBP (mmHg)	125 [115-144]	150 [130-174]	0.002
DBP (mmHg)	77 [72-86]	89 [83-101]	0.001
baPWV (cm/sec)	1413 [1255-1579]	1684 [1568-1907]	0.0003
Hb (g/dL)	14.3 (1.5)	13.4 (2.2)	0.156
Na (mEq/L)	140 [138-141]	139 [138.5-142]	0.395
BUN (mg/dL)	13 [11-16]	15 [13-22]	0.073
Cre (mg/dL)	0.68 [0.53-0.84]	0.84 [0.63-1.39]	0.032
eGFR (mL/min/1.73m ²)	91.2 (26.1)	70.4 (30.6)	0.008
FPG (mg/dL)	152 [126-175]	155 [133-183]	0.444
HbA1c (%)	9.8 (1.9)	10.0 (1.6)	0.636
Fasting CPR (ng/mL)	2.08 [1.55-3.03]	2.06 [1.54-2.51]	0.835
TG (mg/dL)	176 [141-236]	158 [131-236]	0.821
HDL-C (mg/dL)	42 (11)	44 (11)	0.533
LDL-C (mg/dL)	121 (32)	123 (49)	0.877
Plasma osmolality (mOsm/kg)	292.2 (4.6)	296.1 (6.9)	0.040
UACR (mg/gCr)	10.9 [4.9-29.1]	26.2 [8.9-1300.7]	0.023
Duration of diabetes (years)	5.0 [0-11.0]	8.0 [1.0-18.0]	0.121
Smoking, n (%)	32 (62.8)	10 (58.8)	0.781
Metformin, n (%)	26 (51.0)	2 (11.8)	0.005
DPP4i, n (%)	22 (43.1)	11 (64.7)	0.164

SGLT2i, n (%)	18 (35.3)	7 (41.2)	0.773
αGI, n (%)	2 (3.9)	0 (0)	1.000
SU, n (%)	5 (9.8)	2 (11.8)	1.000
Glinide, n (%)	2 (3.9)	1 (5.9)	1.000
TZD, n (%)	0 (0)	0 (0)	
GLP-1 analogue, n (%)	10 (19.6)	1 (5.9)	0.268
Insulin, n (%)	16 (31.4)	6 (35.3)	0.772
Antihypertensive agents, n (%)	28 (54.9)	9 (52.9)	1.000
Diuretic agents, n (%)	6 (11.8)	5 (29.4)	0.126
ACEi or ARB, n (%)	25 (49.0)	8 (47.1)	1.000
Hypolipidemic agents, n (%)	20 (39.2)	7 (41.2)	1.000
Antiplatelet agents, n (%)	7 (13.7)	3 (17.7)	0.702

Data are expressed as mean (standard deviation: SD), median [interquartile range: IQR], or n (%).

Abbreviations: PDR, proliferative diabetic retinopathy; BMI, body mass index; ECW, extracellular water; ICW, intracellular water; ECW/TBW, extracellular water to total body water ratio; BFM, body fat mass; WHR, waist to hip ratio; SMM, skeletal muscle mass; LBM, lean body mass; BMC, bone mineral content; SBP, systolic blood pressure; DBP, diastolic blood pressure; baPWV, brachial-ankle pulse wave velocity; Hb, hemoglobin; Na, sodium; BUN, blood urea nitrogen; Cre, creatinine; eGFR, estimated glomerular filtration rate; FPG, fasting plasma glucose; HbA1c, glycated hemoglobin; CPR, serum C peptide immunoreactivity; TG, triglycerides; HDL-C, high-density lipoprotein cholesterol; LDL-C, low-density lipoprotein cholesterol; UACR, urinary albumin to creatinine ratio; DPP4i, dipeptidyl peptidase-4 inhibitor; SGLT2i, sodium glucose cotransporter 2 inhibitor; αGI, α-glucosidase inhibitor; SU, sulfonylurea; TZD, thiazolidinediones; GLP-1, glucagon-like peptide-1; ACEi, angiotensin-converting enzyme inhibitor; ARB, angiotensin II receptor blocker.

Supplementary Table 2. Comparison of clinical characteristics between the non-PDR and PDR groups in patients aged ≥ 60 years.

Variables	non-PDR (n = 110)	PDR (n = 27)	P Value
Male, n (%)	48 (43.6)	16 (59.3)	0.196
Age (years)	71 [67-77]	71 [66-77]	0.560
Height (cm)	158 (9)	159 (8)	0.622
Body weight (kg)	61.4 [54.6-71.3]	62.5 [56.2-69.2]	0.655
BMI (kg/m ²)	24.6 [21.8-27.7]	24.4 [23.1-27.1]	0.697
ECW (L)	12.0 [10.4-13.6]	13.1 [11.0-14.3]	0.148
ICW (L)	18.1 [15.9-21.0]	19.5 [16.6-21.9]	0.378
ECW/TBW	0.393 [0.388-0.399]	0.398 [0.394-0.407]	0.001
BFM (kg)	19.3 [15.2-25.4]	19.6 [16.6-24.9]	0.972
WHR	0.88 [0.84-0.92]	0.87 [0.81-0.95]	0.542
SMM (kg)	21.6 [18.8-25.4]	23.4 [19.6-26.5]	0.378
LBM (kg)	40.6 [36.0-47.3]	44.4 [37.6-48.8]	0.286
BMC (kg)	2.3 [2.1-2.6]	2.4 [2.2-2.7]	0.319
SBP (mmHg)	136 (18)	143 (20)	0.072
DBP (mmHg)	76 [70-84]	81 [68-87]	0.272
baPWV (cm/sec)	1826 [1601-2065]	1968 [1649-2361]	0.106
Hb (g/dL)	13.4 [12.1-14.4]	12.8 [12.0-13.8]	0.238
Na (mEq/L)	141 [139-142]	141 [139-143]	0.332
BUN (mg/dL)	15 [13-19]	16 [15-19]	0.058
Cre (mg/dL)	0.68 [0.55-0.91]	0.79 [0.66-1.00]	0.020
eGFR (mL/min/1.73m ²)	73.1 (22.4)	62.4 (20.1)	0.025
FPG (mg/dL)	130 [110-156]	129 [114-157]	0.963
HbA1c (%)	8.3 [7.6-9.6]	8.4 [7.8-9.5]	0.961
Fasting CPR (ng/mL)	1.73 [1.10-2.40]	1.45 [0.99-2.45]	0.645
TG (mg/dL)	121 [94-155]	139 [86-176]	0.487
HDL-C (mg/dL)	45 [38-51]	44 [37-60]	0.557
LDL-C (mg/dL)	90 [74-114]	83 [67-107]	0.288
Plasma osmolality (mOsm/kg)	294.6 [291.5-296.8]	296.1 [292.7-298.7]	0.113
UACR (mg/gCr)	13.9 [6.7-36.0]	147.9 [14.9-542.0]	< .0001
Duration of diabetes (years)	14.5 [8.0-22.0]	18.0 [13.0-28.0]	0.042
Smoking, n (%)	52 (47.3)	12 (44.4)	0.832
Metformin, n (%)	54 (49.1)	13 (48.2)	1.000
DPP4i, n (%)	74 (67.3)	17 (63.0)	0.657

SGLT2i, n (%)	34 (30.9)	11 (40.7)	0.365
αGI, n (%)	13 (11.8)	3 (11.1)	1.000
SU, n (%)	35 (31.8)	10 (37.0)	0.650
Glinide, n (%)	7 (6.4)	2 (7.4)	1.000
TZD, n (%)	2 (1.8)	0 (0)	1.000
GLP-1 analogue, n (%)	17 (15.5)	5 (18.5)	0.770
Insulin, n (%)	25 (22.7)	11 (40.7)	0.086
Antihypertensive agents, n (%)	75 (68.2)	19 (70.4)	1.000
Diuretic agents, n (%)	13 (11.8)	5 (18.5)	0.351
ACEi or ARB, n (%)	52 (47.3)	15 (55.6)	0.521
Hypolipidemic agents, n (%)	79 (71.8)	21 (77.8)	0.633
Antiplatelet agents, n (%)	34 (30.9)	11 (40.7)	0.365

Data are expressed as mean (standard deviation: SD), median [interquartile range: IQR], or n (%).

Abbreviations: PDR, proliferative diabetic retinopathy; BMI, body mass index; ECW, extracellular water; ICW, intracellular water; ECW/TBW, extracellular water to total body water ratio; BFM, body fat mass; WHR, waist to hip ratio; SMM, skeletal muscle mass; LBM, lean body mass; BMC, bone mineral content; SBP, systolic blood pressure; DBP, diastolic blood pressure; baPWV, brachial-ankle pulse wave velocity; Hb, hemoglobin; Na, sodium; BUN, blood urea nitrogen; Cre, creatinine; eGFR, estimated glomerular filtration rate; FPG, fasting plasma glucose; HbA1c, glycated hemoglobin; CPR, serum C peptide immunoreactivity; TG, triglycerides; HDL-C, high-density lipoprotein cholesterol; LDL-C, low-density lipoprotein cholesterol; UACR, urinary albumin to creatinine ratio; DPP4i, dipeptidyl peptidase-4 inhibitor; SGLT2i, sodium glucose cotransporter 2 inhibitor; αGI, α-glucosidase inhibitor; SU, sulfonylurea; TZD, thiazolidinediones; GLP-1, glucagon-like peptide-1; ACEi, angiotensin-converting enzyme inhibitor; ARB, angiotensin II receptor blocker.

Supplementary Table 3. Comparison of skeletal muscle mass in non-PDR and PDR groups by age.

Variable	< 60 years old		≥ 60 years old		<i>P</i> ^a Value	<i>P</i> ^b Value	<i>P</i> ^c Value	<i>P</i> ^d Value
	non-PDR (n = 51)	PDR (n = 17)	non-PDR (n = 110)	PDR (n = 27)				
SMM /Height ² (kg/m ²)	10.5 [9.2-11.2]	10.4 [9.7-11.0]	8.8 [8.0-9.6]	9.0 [8.3-9.6]	1.000	0.827	< .0001	0.006

Data are expressed as median [interquartile range: IQR]. *P*^a non-PDR vs. PDR (< 60 years old), *P*^b non-PDR vs. PDR (≥ 60 years old), *P*^c non-PDR (< 60 years old) vs. non-PDR (≥ 60 years old), *P*^d PDR (< 60 years old) vs. PDR (≥ 60 years old).

Abbreviations: PDR, proliferative diabetic retinopathy; SMM, skeletal muscle mass.

Supplementary Table 4. Univariate logistic regression analyses: association between the PDR group and variables in patients aged < 60 years.

	OR	95% CI	<i>P</i> Value
HbA1c (per 1%)	1.076	0.797 - 1.454	0.631
Duration of diabetes (per 1 year)	1.078	1.000 - 1.161	0.049
SBP (per 1 mmHg)	1.044	1.016 - 1.072	0.002
Hb (per 1 g/dL)	0.749	0.540 - 1.038	0.083
TG (per 1 mg/dL)	1.000	0.996 - 1.004	0.915
LDL-C (per 1 mg/dL)	1.001	0.987 - 1.017	0.845
HDL-C (per 1 mg/dL)	1.016	0.966 - 1.069	0.527
Cre (per 0.1 mg/dL)	1.143	1.005 - 1.300	0.041
eGFR (per 1 mL/min/1.73m ²)	0.973	0.952 - 0.994	0.013
UACR (per 10 mg/gCr)	1.019	1.003 - 1.034	0.019
ECW/TBW (per 0.001)	1.197	1.076 - 1.332	0.001

Abbreviations: PDR, proliferative diabetic retinopathy; OR, odds ratio; 95% CI, 95% confidence interval; HbA1c, glycated hemoglobin; SBP, systolic blood pressure; Hb, hemoglobin; TG, triglycerides; LDL-C, low-density lipoprotein cholesterol; HDL-C, high-density lipoprotein cholesterol; Cre, creatinine; eGFR, estimated glomerular filtration rate; UACR, urinary albumin to creatinine ratio; ECW/TBW, extracellular water to total body water ratio.

Supplementary Table 5. Univariate logistic regression analyses: association between the PDR group and variables in patients aged ≥ 60 years.

	OR	95% CI	<i>P</i> Value
HbA1c (per 1%)	0.966	0.725 - 1.288	0.814
Duration of diabetes (per 1 year)	1.047	1.007 - 1.089	0.021
SBP (per 1 mmHg)	1.021	0.998 - 1.045	0.075
Hb (per 1 g/dL)	0.930	0.733 - 1.179	0.548
TG (per 1 mg/dL)	1.003	0.999 - 1.007	0.138
LDL-C (per 1 mg/dL)	0.995	0.980 - 1.010	0.489
HDL-C (per 1 mg/dL)	1.015	0.983 - 1.048	0.371
Cre (per 0.1 mg/dL)	1.146	1.014 - 1.296	0.029
eGFR (per 1 mL/min/1.73m ²)	0.978	0.958 - 0.998	0.028
UACR (per 10 mg/gCr)	1.032	1.013 - 1.051	0.001
ECW/TBW (per 0.001)	1.077	1.027 - 1.129	0.002

Abbreviations: PDR, proliferative diabetic retinopathy; OR, odds ratio; 95% CI, 95% confidence interval; HbA1c, glycated hemoglobin; SBP, systolic blood pressure; Hb, hemoglobin; TG, triglycerides; LDL-C, low-density lipoprotein cholesterol; HDL-C, high-density lipoprotein cholesterol; Cre, creatinine; eGFR, estimated glomerular filtration rate; UACR, urinary albumin to creatinine ratio; ECW/TBW, extracellular water to total body water ratio.

Supplementary Table 6. Comparison of the ECW/TBW by UACR stage.

Variable	Normoalbuminuria (n = 137)	Microalbuminuria (n = 42)	Macroalbuminuria (n = 26)	<i>P</i> ^a Value	<i>P</i> ^b Value	<i>P</i> ^c Value
ECW/TBW	0.390 [0.385-0.396]	0.395 [0.388-0.401]	0.396 [0.390-0.411]	0.104	0.461	0.010

Data are expressed as median [interquartile range: IQR]. The UACR values were classified into three groups: < 30 mg/gCr (Normoalbuminuria), 30–299 mg/gCr (Microalbuminuria), and ≥ 300 mg/gCr (Macroalbuminuria). *P*^a Normoalbuminuria vs. Microalbuminuria, *P*^b Microalbuminuria vs. Macroalbuminuria, *P*^c Normoalbuminuria vs. Macroalbuminuria.

Abbreviations: ECW/TBW, extracellular water to total body water ratio; UACR, urinary albumin to creatinine ratio.